

The Role of Dead Space Length in Biopsy Needles: Image-Guided Percutaneous Core Needle Biopsy: Engineering, Physics, and Clinical Implications

Peter Stibbs^{a,b,c,*}, Daniella Chambers^b, Upender Patel^b

^a *Lakeland Vascular Institute*

^b *University of Nottingham*

^c *Argon Medical Devices Inc.*

Abstract

Image-guided biopsy serves as a pivotal diagnostic modality in the realm of pathologic evaluation. Although considerable scrutiny is often devoted to the needle's cutting length and throw length, the segment known as the "Dead Space Length" frequently remains under-investigated or defined. This manuscript endeavors to elucidate the engineering principles, biomechanical attributes, and clinical ramifications associated with *Dead Space Length* in biopsy needles. Specifically, we focus on its consequential impact on procedural safety metrics and the integrity of acquired tissue samples.

1. Introduction

Image-guided percutaneous core needle biopsy has solidified its role as an indispensable, minimally invasive modality in the diagnostic armamentarium of radiology. The procedure is lauded for its high diagnostic accuracy, reduced morbidity, and cost-effectiveness. While a considerable body of literature has been dedicated to optimizing the "cutting length and "throw length" of the biopsy needles—parameters that directly influence the quality and quantity of the tissue sample—there exists a relative paucity of research focusing on the "Dead Space Length." This term refers to the segment of the stylet that extends beyond the specimen notch and the outer cannula, serving as the terminal point of the needle assembly. The Dead Space Length is not merely an anatomical extension of the needle but serves critical functional roles that have substantial implications for both the safety and efficacy of the biopsy procedure. It acts as a physical barrier to secure the tissue sample within the notch, thereby preventing its dislodgment during the needle's withdrawal. Moreover, the Dead Space Length can influence the needle's trajectory,^[1] thereby affecting the risk of complications, particularly when the target lesion is in close proximity to vital anatomical structures.

*Corresponding author.

Email address: pstibbs@risimaging.com (Peter Stibbs)

Understanding the engineering principles and bio mechanical properties that govern the Dead Space Length is of paramount importance. These principles can offer insights into material selection, frictional dynamics, and even fluid mechanics, all of which contribute to the needle's performance characteristics.

This manuscript aims to provide a comprehensive exploration of the Dead Space Length, delving into its engineering foundations, bio mechanical attributes, and, most importantly, its clinical implications.

2. Engineering and Biomechanics of Dead Space Length: Material Science and Friction

The Dead Space Length is a critical component in securing the tissue sample within the specimen notch as it accounts for the front wall of the tissue notch as an overhang or in design with a closing outer cannula, thereby preventing tissue dislodgment during the extraction process. The choice of material for this segment is of paramount importance. Typically, biocompatible metals such as surgical-grade stainless steel or titanium alloys are employed due to their high tensile strength and resistance to corrosion.^[2]

The surface of the Dead Space Length can be engineered with micro-or nano-scale textures to enhance or reduce frictional forces. According to the Amontons-Coulomb's law of friction, the frictional force F is given by $F = \mu N$, where μ is the coefficient of friction and N is the normal force. By optimizing the surface texture, the coefficient of friction μ can be effectively increased, ensuring that the tissue sample remains securely in place under dynamic conditions such as needle withdrawal or tissue deformation.^[3]

3. Dead Space and Needle Tip Dimensions: A Balance Between Lesion Penetration and Friction Reduction

The dimensions of the Dead Space Length and the needle tip are intricately related and play a pivotal role in the overall performance and safety of a biopsy procedure. Understanding this interplay involves a complex balance between lesion penetration and friction reduction, which are both critical for the successful acquisition of a tissue sample and the minimization of tissue trauma.

Lesion Penetration

The needle tip's sharpness and angle are engineered for optimal penetration through various tissue types, from soft adipose tissue to denser fibrous or calcified lesions. A sharper and more acute angle at the tip allows for easier penetration but may compromise on the tissue sample's integrity. On the other hand, a blunter angle may preserve the tissue better but may require more force for penetration, potentially causing more tissue trauma.

The Dead Space Length, which extends beyond the specimen notch serves as a barrier to keep the acquired tissue sample in place in conjunction with the outer closing cannula. However, if this length is too long, especially in relation to the needle tip dimensions, it could lead to over-penetration, risking injury to vital structures beyond the target lesion.

Figure 1: Dead Space and Tissue Notch

4. Dimensional Synergy

The dimensions of the Dead Space Length and the needle tip must be synergistically designed. For instance, a longer Dead Space Length might be beneficial for securing tissue from fibrotic or calcific lesions but could be detrimental if the needle tip is too sharp or too long, as it could lead to over-penetration or increased friction.^[4] Conversely, a shorter Dead Space Length may reduce the risk of over-penetration but could compromise the sample's integrity, especially if the needle tip is too blunt or too short to penetrate hard or calcific lesions.

5. Computational Modeling for Optimization

Computational models, such as Finite Element Analysis (FEA) and CAD computational measurements, can be used to simulate the effects of various dimensions and materials for both the Dead Space Length and the needle tip.^[5] These models can help in understanding the balance between lesion penetration and friction reduction, thereby aiding in the design of more effective and safer biopsy needles. By understanding the complex interplay between the Dead Space Length and the needle tip dimensions, clinicians and engineers can work together to optimize these features, enhancing both the efficacy and safety of percutaneous core needle biopsies.

6. Safety in Small Lesions

A shorter Dead Space Length minimizes the risk of the needle tip advancing too far and damaging adjacent structures. This is particularly crucial when the target lesion is near vascular structures or sensitive organs. The shorter the Dead Space Length, the less the "throw length," thereby reducing the risk of complications and allowing for less extension of the sharp needle tip beyond the target tissue or lesion.

Precision and Sample Integrity

A shorter Dead Space Length allows for more precise targeting which is essential for smaller lesions. This can be particularly beneficial when using advanced imaging techniques like ultrasound or CT guidance. Moreover, a shorter Dead Space Length reduces the shear stress required to sever the tissue, making it easier to acquire a sample without damaging surrounding structures and keeping within the biopsy target.^[6]

7. The Importance of Needle Trajectory

The trajectory of the biopsy needle is a critical factor that determines the success and safety of the procedure. Deviations from the intended path can lead to complications such as hitting vital structures or missing the target lesion altogether. The trajectory can be influenced by various factors, including the mechanical properties of the needle, the durometer of the tissue being penetrated, and patient-specific anatomical considerations.

Skiving During Actuation

Skiving refers to the unintended lateral movement or deflection of the needle tip during its advancement, particularly when encountering tissues of varying densities or fibrotic regions^[7]. This phenomenon can be particularly problematic when the needle must pass through multiple layers of tissue with different mechanical properties. Skiving can lead to a misalignment of the needle's trajectory, potentially causing it to miss the target lesion or hit a vital structure.

Dead Space Length and Needle Flexion

The Dead Space Length, or the non-cutting tip of the needle, plays a significant role in mitigating the risks associated with skiving and trajectory deviations. A shorter Dead Space Length can provide several advantages.

The Importance of Needle Trajectory: A Deeper Dive

The trajectory of the biopsy needle is not just a straight line from point A to point B; it's a carefully calculated path that must navigate through a complex biological landscape. The trajectory is influenced by the mechanical properties of the needle—such as its rigidity, diameter, and tip design as well as the durometer (hardness) of the tissue being penetrated. Patient-specific anatomical considerations, like the proximity of vital organs or vascular structures, add another layer of complexity. A deviation from the intended trajectory can result in complications ranging from non-diagnostic samples to life-threatening injuries.

Skiving During Actuation: The Underestimated Challenge

Skiving is a phenomenon that often goes unnoticed until it leads to a complication. When the needle encounters tissues of varying densities or fibrotic regions, it may deviate

laterally from its intended path. This is particularly problematic in layered anatomical structures, such as the abdominal wall, where muscle, fat, and fascia each offer different levels of resistance. Skiving can result in a misalignment that either causes the needle to miss the target lesion entirely or, worse, puncture a vital structure like a blood vessel or organ.

**Dead Space Length and Needle Flexion: The Balancing Act
Reduced Flexion**

A shorter Dead Space Length is less prone to flexion, especially when the needle encounters tissues with high durometer values, such as fibrotic lesions or calcifications. Flexion can distort the needle’s trajectory and compromise the integrity of the sample^[8]. By reducing the Dead Space Length, the needle becomes more rigid over its active length at the penetrating tip, making it less susceptible to tip bending and thereby maintaining a more accurate trajectory.

Enhanced Control

The Dead Space Length also plays a crucial role in the operator’s ability to control the needle’s path. A shorter Dead Space Length allows for more precise adjustments during the procedure, especially when navigating through complex anatomical structures. This is particularly beneficial in procedures that require multiple passes or adjustments, such as when targeting small or irregularly shaped lesions.

Reduced Torque

Torque is the rotational force exerted on the needle during its advancement. ^{[9][10]}A shorter Dead Space Length reduces the lever arm through which this force acts, thereby reducing the overall torque. Lower torque levels make it easier to maintain the needle’s intended trajectory, particularly when advancing through tough or fibrotic tissues that might otherwise catch the needle tip causing the needle to deviate.

Figure 2: Needle Skive and Dead Space [4]

8. Safety Considerations

Safety is, of course, the paramount concern in any medical procedure. A shorter Dead Space Length minimizes the risk of over-penetration, which is especially important when the

target lesion is near vital structures.^[6] By reducing the likelihood of over- penetration, clinicians can more confidently approach lesions that are adjacent to organs or vascular structures, thereby expanding the range of lesions that can be safely biopsied.

9. Conclusion

The Dead Space Length in biopsy needles is not merely a structural appendage but a critical, multi-functional component that has far-reaching implications for the safety, efficacy, and success of image-guided percutaneous core needle biopsies. Despite its often overlooked status in the literature and clinical discussions, our comprehensive review underscores its pivotal role in a myriad of factors ranging from tissuesample integrity to procedural safety metrics.

10. References

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